

DETERMINATION THE CONSUMER PREFERENCE MARKET SHARE, MARKET MARGIN, MARKET COST & MARKETING EFFICIENCY

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Abstract

Herbicides are used in agricultural and wildland ecosystems to reduce the density of weeds and promote the growth of desirable species. Use of herbicides in agroecosystems may change composition of weed populations. In wildlands, herbicides may increase the diversity of native species. Threats to plant biodiversity caused by habitat loss and invasive species are far greater than threats by use of herbicides. This article reviews concepts of weeds; principles of weed management; and categories, action, and fate of herbicides. Impacts of herbicides on biodiversity of target and nontarget species and the role of weed control in preserving biodiversity are also discussed. The increase and indiscriminate use of personal care products, food products, fertilizers, pesticides, and health products, among others, have resulted/are resulting in extensive environmental contamination. Most of these products contain traces of widespread chemicals, usually known as emerging pollutants (EPs) or pollutants of emerging concern (PEC). However, there is a gap in information related to the distribution of EPs in the environment of this region, with very few existing review texts exploring this issue. Therefore, this present paper advances this approach. The study shows that the wide distribution and recorded levels of these pollutants in the continental environment are potential risks to human health, mainly through food and drinking water ingestion. Besides that, pharmaceutical products and pesticides are compounds of high consumption worldwide, being environmental contamination a real and ongoing possibility. Finally, gaps and future research needs are deeply pointed out. Herbicides are one of the most recurring pollutants in the aquatic system due to their widespread usage in the agriculture sector for weed control. Semiconductor-based photocatalysts have gained recognition due to their ability to degrade and mineralize pollutants into harmless by-products completely. Lately, many studies have been done to design photocatalysts with efficient separation of photogenerated charge carriers and enhanced light absorption.

Keywords: Herbicides, Habitat loss, Biodiversity, Indiscriminate use, Pollutants, Contamination.

Introduction:

Herbicides also commonly known as weed killers, are substances used to control undesired plants, also known as weeds. Selective herbicides control specific weed species, while leaving the desired crop relatively unharmed, while non-selective herbicides (sometimes called total weeds killers in commercial products) can be used to clear waste ground, industrial and construction sites, railways and railway embankments as they kill all plant material with which they come into contact. Apart from selective/non-selective, other important distinctions include persistence (also known as residual action: how long the product stays in place and remains active), means of uptake (whether it is absorbed by above-ground foliage only, through the roots, or by other means), and mechanism of action (how it works). Historically, products such as common salt and other metal salts were used as herbicides, however these have gradually fallen out of favor and in some countries a number of these are banned due to their persistence in soil, and toxicity and groundwater contaminations concerns

Sinox, the first major organic chemical herbicide, was developed in France in 1896. In the late 1940s new herbicides were developed out of the research during world war2 & the era of the "miracle" weeds killers began. Within 20 years over 100 new chemicals were synthesized, developed, and put into use. Chemical weed control superseded both plant-disease and insect-pest control in economic impact. In particular, the year 1945 was key to the development of selective chemical weed control. Introduced then were 2,4-D (2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid), 2,4,5-T (2,4,5-trichlorophenoxyacetic acid), and IPC (isopropyl-N-phenylcarbamate)—the first two selective as foliar sprays against broad-leaved weeds, the third selective against grass species when applied through the soil. The new herbicides were revolutionary in that their high toxicity allowed for effective weed control at dosage rates as low as one to two kilograms per hectare (one or two pounds per acre). This contrasted with, borax, and arsenic trioxide, which were required at rates of up to 2,242 kilograms per hectare (one ton per acre), and with sodium chlorate, required at rates of around 112 kilograms per hectare (100 pounds per acre). However, some of those early herbicides, including 2,4,5-T, were later deemed unsafe for humans and the environment

and were discontinued in many countries. Effective herbicides have continued to be developed, and some, such as glyphosate, are widely used around the world.

UPL Limited, formerly **United Phosphorus Limited**, is an Indian multinational company that manufactures and markets agrochemicals, industrial chemicals, chemical intermediates, and specialty chemicals, and also offers crop protection solutions. Headquartered in Mumbai, Maharashtra, the company engages in both agro and non-agro activities. The agro business is the company's primary source of revenue and includes the manufacture and marketing of conventional agrochemical products, seeds and other agricultural related products. The non-agro segment includes the manufacture and marketing of industrial chemical and other nonagricultural related products such as fungicides, herbicides, insecticides, plant growth and regulators, rodenticides, industrial and specialty chemicals, and nutrifeds. UPL products are sold in 150+ countries.

UPL Iris Herbicide is designed specifically for soybeans. This weed killer has strong residual activity and controls most weeds throughout the soybean growing season. It is rainfast and effective within 2 hours. It is applied post-emergence at 15 to 25 days after sowing the soybeans when weeds are at the two to four-leaf stage. UPL Iris is moderately toxic, but there is no known antidote. Always wear protective clothing while using the herbicide and keep away from food and animal feed. The UPL Iris Herbicide contains Sodium Acifluorfen 16.5% and Clodinafop-P, a supporting agent. It is applied at a rate of 400ml per acre or hectare. Unlike other post-emergent weed killers, UPL Iris Herbicide is not a pre-emergence herbicide. The application rate is 400ml per acre or hectare, and it is highly effective at destroying grassy weeds in one spray.

Soybean is a major crop grown during the kharif or monsoon season (July-October) in the dry land areas of central and peninsular India. Madhya Pradesh is known as major soybean producer of India, comprising 55 per cent of the total national area of soybean cultivation. Implementation of effective weed control strategies is an important component of soybean production. Control efforts become economically justified because of the potential for soybean yield reduction, crop quality loss, harvesting difficulties, or other problems

associated with the presence of weeds. In some situations, however, low weed populations may not interfere with crop yield, harvestability, or crop quality. This study was conducted during 2021- 2022 in 2 villages of sagar of vindhyan pleasure agro-climatic zone of Madhya Pradesh.

Materials and Methods:

The study entitled “**Determination the consumer preference market share, market margin, market cost & marketing efficiency of Iris herbicide**” was undertaken to assess the consumer preference of Iris herbicide. The study was conducted in Sagar District of Madhya Pradesh.

The present study was mainly based on primary data. The required primary data were collected from selected farmers and Agri-input shops for the agricultural year 2021-22. The requisite secondary data were collected from various published records of government offices, hooks, block development offices, reports, related, websites and other related sources. The consumer behaviour and product preference was be identified through personnel interview of UPL limited users, For achieving the stated objective, the analytical tools such as tables, charts and graphs simple ranking, percentage method were used. Multistage stratified random sampling procedure was adopted for the present investigation to select the ultimate unit of the sample.

From the selected village list of all the UPL limited cultivators obtained from the village development office in each selected village. For the selection of cultivators from families were listed and about 10% farmers were randomly selected from each village and then farmers were classified in to three groups.

The study was entirely based on primary data collected from the selected farmer and different market functionaries. Well-constructed

and pre-tested questionnaire and scheduled (appendix) were used to collect the data on marketing. For collecting the data, personal interviews were arranged and reconnaissance study were also conducted to collect the data regarding market cost, price received and price paid, etc. from growers, different market functionaries and Shahabad growers. Further the required secondary data to supplement the primary data and to support the study were collected from different sources like- Block office and District office, relevant magazines and Internet etc. Data was analyzed with the help of tool like: Percentage analysis, percentage and chi square test,

Study design and place of the study:

Multistage stratified random sampling procedure was adopted for the present investigation to select the ultimate unit of the sample. Chandauli was selected purposively for the present study on the basis of maximum area.

Sample:

The present study consisted of sample 120 respondents from 5 villages namely Sarkhari, chainpura, Sagoni, Semadama, Jaisinagar

Analysis of Data:

The collected data was interpreted and arranged by statistical package for social sciences-16 (SPSS 16) which was specially designed for this purpose.

Results and Discussion:

The study entitled “**Determination the consumer preference market share, market margin, market cost & marketing efficiency of Iris herbicide**” was undertaken to assess the consumer preference of Iris herbicide. The results are given under the following heads:

Table 1: Consumer’s preference towards Iris herbicide (UPL) over other brand

Respondents	UPL	Bayer	Syngenta	Crystal	BSF
R1	5	4	3	4	3
R2	5	4	3	5	3
R3	5	4	3	1	4
R4	4	4	3	2	5
R5	5	3	3	5	5
R6	5	4	3	5	1
R7	2	3	3	4	3
R8	5	3	3	4	5
R9	3	3	4	4	2
R10	5	3	4	4	5
R11	3	3	4	2	1
R12	2	3	4	2	1
R13	4	3	2	2	2
R14	3	5	2	2	2
R15	5	5	2	5	2
R16	3	5	2	5	2
R17	1	5	2	5	2
R18	4	5	5	1	4
R19	5	5	5	2	4
R20	5	4	5	3	5
R21	5	3	5	4	3
R22	5	1	5	5	3
R23	3	1	5	5	5
R24	4	1	5	5	5
R25	4	2	5	2	5
R26	5	4	2	3	5

R27	5	5	2	3	2
R28	4	5	2	1	2
R29	3	4	1	1	2
R30	5	4	1	1	2

In total 30 respondents, were highly preferred where 5 respondents were strongly agreed, 4 were agreed, 3 were neutral, 2 were disagreed and no one were strongly disagreed followed by UPL where 15 respondents were strongly agreed, 6 were agreed, 6 were neutral, 2 were disagreed and no one were strongly disagreed. After that, respondents prefer Bayer where 8 respondents were strongly agreed, 9 were agreed, 9 were neutral, 1 were disagreed and 3 one were strongly disagreed. After that, respondents prefer symgenta where 8 respondents were strongly agreed, 9 were agreed, 8 were neutral, 8 were disagreed and 2 were strongly disagreed. After that, respondents prefer Crystal where 9 respondents were strongly agreed, 6 were agreed, 3 were neutral, 7 were disagreed and 5 one were strongly disagreed. After that, respondents prefer BSF where 9 respondents were strongly agreed, 3 were agreed, 5 were neutral, 10 were disagreed and 3 were strongly disagreed.

Market share is calculated by taking the companies sales over the period and dividing it by the total sales of company over the same period.

Table 2: Market share of different companies for herbicide sales in Sagar district (2021- 2022)

Sl.No	Company name	Brand name	Quantity sale	Value (in lakh)	Market share (%)
1	Bayer	Nrtivo (kg)	1800	26.32	17.66
2	UPL	Iris (lit)	930	48.15	32.30
3	Syngenta	Taspa (lit)	1190	20.29	24.25
4	Crystal	Amora	860	20.29	13.62
5	Other		712	18.12	12.17
Total			6952	149.03	100

The market share of several herbicide firms is shown in Table. According to the research, UPL Company has the largest market share (32.30 percent), followed by Syngenta (24.25 percent), Bayer (17.66 percent), Crystal (13.62 percent), and others (12.17 percent).

Fig 1 Company wise Turnover of Herbicide in Sagar District (2020-21)

Table 3: Marketing Margin Marketing cost & Marketing Efficiency of "Iris herbicide"

S. No	Particular	Rs	Percentage
1	Net price received by producer	1150	85.18
2	Marketing cost incurred by producer	150	11.12
3	Price paid by trader	1300	96.29
4	Expenses incurred by trader	75	5.56
5	Margin of trader	100	7.40
6	Price paid by wholesaler	1250	92.59
7	Expenses incurred by wholesaler	70	5.18

8	Margin of wholesaler	150	11.12
9	Price paid by processor	1310	97.03
10	Total marketing cost	170	12.59
11	Total marketing margin	200	14.81
12	Consumer price	1350	100
13	Marketing efficiency	209	15.48

Fig 2: For money

Conclusion:

The study concludes that the farmer respondents are conscious mainly about the quality and are insensitive to price in case of availability of good quality herbicide. The detailed interviews with the farmer respondents spelt out that the brand switching behaviour has been influenced mainly by the fellow farmers and also due to the price difference between the Iris brands. Concerning brand loyalty, there were varied choices made by the farmers in different situations but the majority were found to be loyal to both the brand and the dealers. From the Covid-19 market study, it was inferred and evident that there will be a increasing rate of brand loyal farmers in the next season. Adding to this it is also observed that field demonstrations are considered the most influencing promotional tool due to direct visibility of the results. Therefore, brand loyalty can be maintained by the companies by conducting field demonstrations or any other promotional tool wherein the results are visible to the farmers directly. Also, in case of distribution channels, all the channels had the primary dealers which imply that major pricing power might rest with them as some sell directly to the farmers and attain greater margin due to direct sale to end customer.

All these factors majorly point towards the timely availability of quality with affordable prices to be the appropriate requirements of the farmer.

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